

MODERN ASPECTS OF THE TREATMENT OF LICHEN PLANUS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA**Mammadova S.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Associate Professor
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Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495315>**Abstract**

Lichen planus (LP) is a nodular chronic disease that occurs on the skin and visible mucous membranes. With this disease, the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and the red border of the lips are often affected. The disease is more common in women aged 40 to 65 years. The causes of lichen planus have not been fully elucidated. There are neurogenic, viral, bacterial, autoimmune theories of this disease. Recently, there has been a "rejuvenation" of those suffering from this disease. This is due to increased contact with a viral infection, a significant change in the reactivity of the body, as well as an increased frequency of psycho-emotional stress.

Keywords: lichen planus, erosive form of lichen planus, hyperkeratotic form of lichen planus, nonspecific resistance.

Relevance

To date, the disease lichen planus remains an urgent problem associated with the constant frequency of its detection, the lack of a single pathogenetic concept, as well as the presence of severe forms and a chronic course, often resistant to ongoing therapy.

At present, there is no doubt that without the presentation and integration of fundamental research to explain the causes of occurrence, the mechanisms of development of many chronic diseases, including dental ones, it is impossible to carry out prevention, adequate treatment with prolongation into a stable and long-term remission. Lichen planus (LP) is a serious disease with a rather complex, not fully understood and still largely controversial mechanism of development [1], often ineffective treatment outcome [2], with an unstable, even short remission period [3] and high the likelihood of malignancy of lesions, primarily with a violation of the integrity of the oral mucosa (SPR) [5].

The disease occurs more often in the age group from 30 to 60 years, although recently there has been a "rejuvenation" of those suffering from this disease [7]. Perhaps this is due to increased contact with a viral infection, a significant change in the reactivity of the body, as well as an increased frequency of psycho-emotional stress [4].

Isolated lesions of the oral mucosa are noted in 70% of cases. Most often, the process develops on the mucous membrane of the cheeks, tongue, in the retromolar region, gums, lips, very rarely in the region of the floor of the mouth and palate.

It should be noted that the captious view of researchers on this disease is due to the significant frequency of its associations with chronic diseases of in-

ternal organs and systems [6]. The latter factors, undoubtedly having an impact on the characteristics of the course of LP, determine the search for other integrated approaches to treatment.

In recent years, certain progress has been made in the study of the CPL of SSMS. Some causative factors of the disease have been clarified, including the influence of somatic pathology on the formation of the pathological process; a connection between the CPL and some occupational hazards, exposure to medicinal substances and filling materials has been established; aspects of the combination of LP ORM with other dermatoses and the possibility of transforming individual forms of the disease into oncogenic ones are reflected. The most common concepts for the development of LP are: immunological, hereditary, viral, neurogenic, endocrine, etc.

To date, drugs for the treatment of erosive and ulcerative forms of lichen planus include the use of general and local medicines. There are many drugs for oral use. Glucocorticosteroids are prescribed as basic therapy. The clinical effectiveness of vitamin therapy on metabolic processes (vitamins A, E, C) has been shown. An important role in the treatment of LP of the oral mucosa is played by local therapy (applications with corticosteroid ointments, anti-inflammatory and epithelial agents). There are reports in the literature about the treatment of patients with lichen planus by injections under erosion with vitamin B1 or nicotinic acid. Recently, immunotropic therapy for lichen planus has been increasingly used. However, the ointments, oils, creams and pastes used do not simultaneously have an adhesive, anti-inflammatory and angioprotective effect. Such treatment does not prevent the development of relapses of the disease [7].

Materials and methods of research

A total of 50 patients were under observation, aged 32 to 75 years, among whom were 24 men and 26 women. The subjects were divided into 3 groups, depending on the local treatment. General treatment in all groups consisted of taking "Persen" 1 capsule 3 times a day, prednisolone 25 mg every other day. The first group consisted of 10 patients who underwent traditional local treatment: applications of sea buckthorn oil, 5% anesthesin solution in peach oil for 20 minutes 3-4 times a day.

The second group included 20 patients, in which local therapy was carried out using the developed ointment, which includes hydrocortisone, "Solcoseryl dental adhesive" paste, 5% solution of vitamin "C", vitamins "A" and "E".

In the third group, 20 patients were treated with the same ointment in combination with Imudon.

Characteristics of the components of a poly-component adhesive ointment (PAM).

Vitamins "C", "A" and "E" have an antioxidant effect, help strengthen the walls of the microvascular bed of the oral mucosa. Solcoseryl dental adhesive paste provides accelerated healing, pain relief and protection of the wound surface. In addition, the paste provides high adhesion of the medicinal components introduced into the composition to the wet mucous membrane, and, as a result, guarantees a long-term deposition of all PAM medicinal components on its surface. Hydrocortisone has an anti-inflammatory effect, and also promotes the epithelization of erosions.

Imudon is an immunostimulating agent. The drug was used in the form of tablets, which were recommended to dissolve in the mouth without chewing, with an interval of 2 hours.

The evaluation of the clinical effectiveness of the treatment methods carried out was carried out by daily measuring the area of the altered mucous membrane using a millimeter grid according to the formula: $S = m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 / n$, where m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4 is the area of each erosion on the inner surface of the cheeks, palate, gums and lips, n is the number of measurements.

It was noted that the effect of local treatment in the first group was significantly lower than in the second and third. The main disadvantage of the local treatment of the first group was that the agents used were easily washed off with saliva and food, so the anti-inflammatory and angioprotective effect did not have a stable therapeutic effect, the healing of papules on the mucous membrane proceeded slowly.

In the second group, the processes of epithelialization were faster than in the first, including due to the good adhesion of the ointment to the moist oral mucosa. On the 28th day, healing of 73.5% of formations was observed.

In the third group, on the 28th day, 95.1% of patients had complete healing of papules of the oral mucosa. Allergic reactions and complications during treatment were not observed.

Conclusion

The data obtained showed that the treatment in the first group was not effective enough compared to the second and third groups. The use of the developed ointment (second group), especially in combination with "Imudon" (third group) made it possible to accelerate the healing of papular rashes, prevent the development of complications and reduce the period of complete epithelialization of the affected mucosa in lichen planus.

References:

1. Belenchuk T.A. Metody otsenki mestnykh zashchitnykh prichin v polosti rta /T.A. Belenchuk, Yu.A. Samoilo, S.M. Zakharova i dr. // Novye metody diagnostiki i rezul'taty ikh vnedreniya v stomatologicheskuyu praktiku: tr. TsNIIS. – M., 1991. –№ 2–11. – S. 43–46.
2. Perlamutrov Yu.N. Otsenka effektivnosti i perenosimosti immunosupressivnoi terapii v kompleksnom lechenii krasnoi ploskoi lishayaslizistoi obolochki polosti rta / Yu.N. Perlamutrov, A.V. Tereshchenko, G.V. Vykh, Yu.P. Glazkova // Klinicheskaya dermatologiya i venerologiya. – 2010. – № 4. – S. 40–44.
3. Spitsyna V.I., Patogenez immunodefitsita u bol'nykh krasnym ploskim lishaem slizistoi obolochki polosti rta // Rus. stomat. zhurnal. – 2002. – № 3. –S. 30-33.15. Tkachenko P.I. Immunologicheskii apparat slizistoi polosti rta: sovremennoe sostoyanie voprosa (obzor literatury) / P.I. Tkachenko // Vestnik stomatologii. – Odessa, 2002. – № 4. –S. 130–134
4. Makedonova Yu. A., Fedotova Yu. M., Firsova I. V., Poroiskii S. V. SOVREMENNYE ASPEKTY LEChENIYa EROZIVNO-YaZVENNOI FORMY KRASNOGO PLOSKOGO LISHAYa SLIZISTOI OBOLOChKI POLOSTI RTA // Sovremennye problemy nauki i obrazovaniya. – 2016. – № 2.
5. Khanova S.A., Sirak S.V., Chebotarev V.V., Sirak A.G. KRASNYI PLOSKII LISHAI SLIZISTOI OBOLOChKI POLOSTI RTA, SOVREMENNYE METODY MESTNOGO LEChENIYa // Mezhdunarodnyi zhurnal prikladnykh i fundamental'nykh issledovaniy. – 2014. – № 2. – S. 197-202;
6. Roopashree M.R. Immune mechanisms in oral lichen planus / M.R. Roopashree, M.H. Thornhill // Acta Odontol. Scand. – 2001, Jun; 59 (3):174–7.
7. Breathnach S.M. Lichen Planus and Lichenoid Disorders. Rook's Text book of Dermatology. 8-th. // Ed. Dermatology, 2010.